

Tool Artifact for “On Synthesizing Presence Conditions in Numerical Software Product Lines”

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Abstract. In this work, we describe the installation, usage, and evaluation results of the tool, denoted `SPLSynthesize`, introduced by the paper “On Synthesizing Presence Conditions in Numerical Software Product Lines”. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to download, run, and compare the tool’s outputs to outputs described in the paper. The tool is a research prototype synthesizer designed for automatically synthesizing assertion-safe `#ifdef`-guards in numerical Software Product Lines (SPLs). It uses a combination of forward and backward lifted static analyses of SPLs based on abstract interpretation to generate constraints that are subsequently solved by using the logical abduction technique.

1 Introduction

This work summarises the evaluation results reported by the paper “On Synthesizing Presence Conditions in Numerical Software Product Lines”. Our prototype tool, `SPLSynthesize`, calls the following tools. The abstract operations and transfer functions of the numerical abstract domains (e.g. Polyhedra [1]) are provided by the APRON library [6], while the decision-tree and tuple-based lifted domains are provided by the `SPLNUM2ANALYZER` tool [4]. The abduction and SMT queries are solved by the EXPLAIN [2] and the MISTRAL [3] tools. We compare three versions of our tool:

- **Decision-tree** approach that uses decision-tree lifted analyses for constraint generation.
- **Tuple-based** approach that uses tuple-based lifted analyses for constraint generation.
- **Variability encoding**-based approach that transforms an input SPL into a single program and uses single-program analyses for constraint generation.

2 Downloading

2.1 VM

The URL of the VM that contains the tool artifact is available from the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/15092472>.

The files inside this folder are:

- Ubuntu18-1.7z.001 ("md5Checksum": "e10e1a874f8673051235dc22ee51849c"),
- Ubuntu18-1.7z.002 ("md5Checksum": "65bbf8b294c9ee6b2cd14e5f45413d17"),
- Ubuntu18-1.7z.003 "md5Checksum": "af2059b549fd5ddb4048f4386a224973",
- Ubuntu18-1.7z.004 ("md5Checksum": "0c184000896722984b6a5d548a2018b5")

Once you download all files, use 7-Zip to restore VM image “Ubuntu18-1.ova”. The virtual machine containing the tool installed and ready to use is “user”: aleks, “password”: aleks.

2.2 tar.gz file

To install the tool by yourself, download the file: SPLSynthesize.tar.gz ("md5Checksum": "5b39b7486df0bb03373159bcb62d1d82") from the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/15092472>.

* Untar the given file:

```
tar -xvf SPLSynthesize.tar.gz
```

* Enter the folder that contains the tools

```
cd SPLSynthesize
```

* For step-by-step installation of the tools follow:

```
HowToInstall.txt
```

* Note that you have to install Ocaml, Apron, and MISTRAL. The MISTRAL SMT Solver has been tested to compile only on **Ubuntu 12.04 and Ubuntu 18.04**.

3 Experimental Results

* For step-by-step execution of all test cases of the tools follow:

```
ExperimentalResults.txt
```

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd SPLSynthesize
```

Note that after commands in square brackets we write:

- the obtained solution,
- the total times in seconds on our machine to complete the given synthesis task, and
- the time taken to solve the given abduction queries by calling EXPLAIN.

The above results are reported in Table 1 as well. From the output of the tool, you can additionally see:

- abstract syntax of the input program,
- the results inferred by Forward Analysis and Backward UnderApproximating Analysis at all locations of the input program,
- the Forward Invariant before the hole, and two Backward Conditions after the hole where the first one includes the effect of the protected statement and the second one does not include the effects of the protected statement,
- the abduction solver returns R_{true} and R_{false} predicates.

3.1 Decision-tree based approach

To run SPLSynthesize, version Decision-tree based approach, on the examples from the paper [5] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/intro.c
result: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 5$ ), [0.752 sec], [0.740 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/intro-b.c
result: Hole1: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 49$ ), Hole2: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 5$ ), [3.076 sec], [2.996]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/spl.c
result: ( $A > 5 \ \& \ A \leq 49 \ \& \ B = 1$ ), [0.772 sec], [0.755 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/spl-b.c
result: Hole1: ( $A > 5 \ \& \ A \leq 49 \ \& \ B = 1$ ), Hole2: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 49 \ \& \ 0 \leq B \leq 1$ ),
[3.146 sec], [3.007]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/minmax.c
result: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 5$ ), [0.751 sec], [0.738 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/while.c
result: ( $A \geq 0 \ \& \ A \leq 1$ ), [0.780 sec], [0.766 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/mine.c
result: ( $A > 5 \ \& \ A \leq 10$ ), [0.771 sec], [0.742 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/Mysore.c
result: ( $A > 2 \ \& \ A \leq 49 \ \& \ 0 \leq B \leq 1$ ), [0.781 sec], [0.751 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/apr_signal_block.c
result: ( $SIGPIPE\_A > 5 \ \& \ SIGPIPE\_A \leq 99$ ), [0.762 sec], [0.748 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -dt bench/shutdown_signal.c
result: ( $ENABLE\_DEBUG\_INIT > 5 \ \& \ ENABLE\_DEBUG\_INIT \leq 99$ ),
[0.738 sec], [0.726 sec]
```

3.2 Tuple based approach

To run SPLSynthesize, version Tuple based approach, on the examples from the paper [5] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/intro.c
result: ( $\neg(A = 6) \ \& \ \neg(A = 7) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49)$ ), [1.112 sec], [1.005 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/intro-b.c
result: Hole1: (true), Hole2: ( $\neg(A = 6) \ \& \ \neg(A = 7) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49)$ ), [4.441
sec], [4.231]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/spl.c
result: ( $\neg(B = 1) \vee (\neg(A = 0) \ \& \ \neg(A = 1) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 5))$ ) & ( $\neg(B = 0) \vee$ 
 $\neg(A = 0) \ \& \ \neg(A = 1) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49)$ )), [2.103 sec], [2.011 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/spl-b.c
result: Hole1: ( $\neg(B = 1) \vee (\neg(A = 0) \ \& \ \neg(A = 1) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 5))$ ) & ( $\neg(B =$ 
 $0) \vee (\neg(A = 0) \ \& \ \neg(A = 1) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49))$ ), Hole2: (true), [9.201 sec], [8.120]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/minmax.c
result: ( $\neg(A = 6) \ \& \ \neg(A = 7) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49)$ ), [1.468 sec], [1.337 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/while.c
result: ( $\neg(A = 2) \ \& \ \neg(A = 3) \ \& \ \dots \ \& \ \neg(A = 49)$ ), [1.486 sec], [1.243 sec]
```

```

$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/mine.c
result: ( $\neg(A = 0) \& \neg(A = 1) \& \dots \& \neg(A = 5) \& \neg(A = 11) \& \dots \& \neg(A = 49)$ ),
[2.033 sec], [1.821 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/Mysore.c
result: ( $\neg(A = 0) \& \neg(A = 1) \& \neg(A = 2)$ ), [3.158 sec], [2.234 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/apr_signal_block.c
result: ( $\neg(SIGPIPE\_A = 0) \& \dots \& \neg(SIGPIPE\_A = 5)$ ), [1.188 sec], [1.068
sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -tuple bench/shutdown_signal.c
result: ( $\neg(ENABLE\_DEBUG\_INIT = 0) \& \dots \& \neg(ENABLE\_DEBUG\_INIT =
5)$ ), [1.882 sec], [1.588 sec]

```

3.3 Variability encoding based approach

To run SPLSynthesize, version Variability encoding based approach, on the examples from the paper [5] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```

$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/intro-single.c
result: ( $A \leq 5$ ), [6.766 sec], [6.751 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/intro-b-single.c
result: Hole1: (false), Hole2: ( $A \leq 2$ ), [3.018 sec], [3.001]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/spl-single.c
result: (false), [0.767 sec], [0.758 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/spl-b-single.c
result: Hole1: false, Hole2: (true), [2.983 sec], [2.950]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/minmax-single.c
result: (false), [0.730 sec], [0.723 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/while-single.c
result: (false), [0.741 sec], [0.726 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/mine-single.c
result: (false), [0.766 sec], [0.749 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/Mysore-single.c
result: (false), [0.762 sec], [0.735 sec]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/apr_signal_block-single.c
result: [timeout]
$ time ./Main.native -domain polyhedra -single bench/shutdown_signal-single.c
result: [timeout]

```

4 Extensibility

The tool is written in OCAML and consists of around 7K LOC. Currently, it provides only a limited support for arrays, pointers, `struct` and `union` types. The abstract operations and transfer functions of the numerical abstract domains (e.g. Polyhedra [1]) are provided by the APRON library [6], while the decision-tree and tuple-based lifted domains are provided by the SPLNUM²ANALYZER tool

Table 1. Performance results of Decision-tree vs. Tuple vs. Variability encoding-based approaches. All times in sec. All experiments are executed on a 64-bit 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM LUbuntu 18.04 with 4 GB memory.

Bench.	\mathcal{K}	Decision-tree			Tuple			Variability encod.		
		TIME	AbdTime	Prec	TIME	AbdTime	Prec	TIME	AbdTime	Prec
intro.c	50	0.752	0.740	✓	1.112	1.005	✓	6.766	6.751	✓
intro-b.c	50	3.076	2.996	✓	4.441	4.231	✓	3.018	3.001	≈
spl.c	100	0.772	0.755	✓	2.103	2.011	✓	0.767	0.758	≈
spl-b.c	100	3.146	3.007	✓	9.201	8.120	✓	2.983	2.950	≈
minmax.c	50	0.751	0.738	✓	1.468	1.337	✓	0.730	0.723	≈
while.c	50	0.780	0.766	✓	1.486	1.243	✓	0.741	0.726	≈
mine.c	50	0.771	0.742	✓	2.033	1.821	✓	0.766	0.749	≈
Mysore.c	100	0.781	0.751	✓	3.158	2.234	✓	0.762	0.735	≈
apr_signal.c	100	0.762	0.748	✓	1.188	1.168	✓	timeout		
shutdown_sig.c	100	0.738	0.726	✓	1.882	1.588	✓	timeout		

[4]. The abduction and SMT queries are solved by the EXPLAIN [2] and the MISTRAL [3] tools.

In the folder “frontend”, the lexer and parser are implemented. In the folder “main”, the files “Main.ml”, “DTAnalysisIterator”, “TupleAnalysisIterator”, and “SingleAnalysisIterator” describe the main program from which the tool performs analysis of the given SPL and the implementation of the forward and backward analyses for the three approaches: Decision-tree, Tuple, and Variability encoding, respectively. The tool can be easily extended and new options can be added.

References

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